

Nihilism in the Sahara: Exploring the Moresbys' Physical and Psychological Itineraries in Paul Bowles' *The Sheltering Sky*

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Abstract:

Paul Bowles's *The Sheltering Sky* is an existential narrative that explores both a physical and psychological journey into the North African Sahara desert and the human psyche. It portrays the intertwined itineraries of the protagonists, Port and Kit Moresby, as they traverse the desolate landscape and navigate their tumultuous inner worlds. The couple, joined by their friend Tunner, leaves Western civilization hoping to mend their fractured marriage. Their journey, however, turns into a nightmarish odyssey of alienation and despair. The desolate desert mirrors their psychological descent into nihilism, stripping them of their cultural identities and forcing them

to confront their existential anxieties. Drawing on Sartre's existentialism, this paper delves into themes of nothingness and absurdity, exploring a harrowing yet profound journey of self-discovery.

Keywords: Paul Bowles, existentialism, nihilism, self-discovery, North African Sahara.

Introduction

Two ideas are preeminent in Paul Bowles' fiction in general and in his North African novels in particular: the destructiveness of modern Western civilization and the quest for an alternative way of life, away from it, in exotic places. These two ideas are closely related in his writings, with the relationship between them being one of cause and effect. The search of Bowles' characters for a different pattern of life elsewhere is the immediate outcome of their dissatisfaction with the conditions of life in their modern societies. It is only when no reconciliation is possible between these characters and their societies that they resort to

traveling abroad as a solution. The destinations usually chosen by Bowles' characters are foreign places that are different from the world they have left behind. The places they move to should be less infected by the disease of modern civilization. Bowles' views about the manifestations of progress in modern societies are extremely skeptical. He entirely rejects modern civilization in its present American version. He is also doubtful about what is known as *progress*. Bowles is convinced that it is erroneous to dub a process leading to the destruction of humanity as *progress*.

The Sheltering Sky chronicles a thrilling and captivating adventure into the abysmal and hostile North African Sahara desert, and the

unfathomable depths of the human psyche correspondingly. This existential piece of fiction recounts the story of the Moresbys, a couple of American expatriates, who leave Western civilization – with their friend Tunner – to embark on an adventurous journey to the fascinating desert region of North Africa with high hopes of restoring their broken marriage. However, this promising travel turns out to be a nightmarish travel to the unknown. The unprecedented choice of such a setting reflects Paul Bowles' enthralling relationship with North Africa, where he spent most of his life. He knows the region very well since he travelled the whole area. The aim of this paper is to trace the physical journey of Port and Kit and demystify their psychological itinerary throughout their startling adventure.

The Moresbys' Physical Itinerary

The Sheltering Sky is a tripartite. The first part, which is entitled "Tea in the Sahara", begins in Oran, an Algerian city that has most of the comforts that Europeans need when traveling abroad. The travel to North Africa was Port's idea. The Moresbys are not simply tourists, they are travelers "belonging no more to one place than to the next" (Bowles, 1990, p. 79). They are not planning to go back home. After ten years of marriage, Port and Kit seem to be alienated and emotionally estranged from each other. Port hopes that this venturesome undertaking will restore their broken relationship. However, they see the desert differently. Port finds the desert fascinating, whereas Kit is afraid of it. Tunner is the third part of the love triangle. His presence sometimes alleviates the tension between the couple through attracting their attention to mundane matters, but he can also be seen as a threat to their reunion since he prevents intimacy and later seduces Kit. Port, one night, suspects this and goes on a walk, ending up in bed with an Arab prostitute who robs him. The three Americans meet the disagreeable Eric Lyle and his nagging mother, an English couple, at the Grand Hotel in Oran. The Lyles seem determined to keep company with the Americans on their adventures.

When the Lyles offer them a ride to Boussif on their car, Kit refuses and takes the train with Tunner, even though Port first objects her decision because he does not want her to be alone with Tunner. On the train, however, she yields to Tunner's temptation under the spell of a suitcase full of champagne. Once in Boussif, Port tries to get closer to his wife, but his attempts are disrupted by the presence of Tunner or Eric Lyle and baffled by his absorption in the desert and the "silences and emptiness that touched his soul" (Bowles, 1990, p. 80).

From Boussif, Port, Kit and Tunner head to the fly-infested filthy town of Ain Krorfa. The only hotel in town, Carrion Towers, has piles of garbage in its lobby and an overwhelming odor of waste all around. Once there, Port arranges for Tunner to leave to Messad with the Lyles to separate him from Kit. Then, the Moresbys travel to the French military outstation of Bou Noura alone.

The events of the second part, "The Earth's Sharp Edge", take place in Bou Noura, where Port finds out that his passport was stolen by Eric Lyle. From Bou Noura, Kit and Port travel to El Ga'a, where there is the threat of a meningitis epidemic. Port is seriously sick and is barely conscious, by the time they get there. Because of the imminent epidemic, they are not granted entrance to the town's only hotel. Fortunately, Kit finds a truck heading to Sba, where they meet Mr. Broussard, a local French captain, who identifies Port's illness as typhoid and provides them with shelter, soup and pills. However, Port succumbs to typhoid and dies. Consequently, Kit enters a slow process of abjection and self-destruction as she runs out of town towards the desert.

In the novel's third part, "The Sky", Kit is rescued by a trading caravan led by Belqassim and his older friend; they take turns raping her in what becomes a daily ritual. However, she bizarrely falls in love with Belqassim. He takes her south to his home, disguising her as an Arab boy to hide her identity from his wives, and imprisons her in a locked room. His other three jealous wives attack her as soon as they find out

the truth about her. As a result, Belqasim marries Kit and makes her a fourth wife. She decides to escape when his greatly desired visits to the marital chamber in which she is locked up become less frequent. She swaps the jewelry she was given at her wedding with some women who help her escape.

Kit is now increasingly perturbed. She spends the night in a hotel with a local, named Amar, who helps her, but later robs her. Eventually, someone takes her to a group of nuns who, after discovering her identity, hand her to the American consulate who arrange her passage back to the United States. Before that, Kit, shaken and unresponsive, is taken back to Oran, where Tunner is supposedly waiting for her. Alas, Kit disappears and slips away before she can be returned home.

The Moresby's Psychological Itinerary

Apparently, the journey to the Sahara desert of North Africa is meant to restore the broken relationship between Port and Kit. They have been married for ten years, and now they seem drifting apart as they sleep in separate rooms. In fact, travelling throughout the unfathomable and abysmal Sahara was Port's idea. Kit would have liked to travel to Europe, but her husband convinced her to embark on this adventurous trip to North Africa after showing her "a carefully chosen collection of photographs" (Bowles, 1990, p. 88). Most probably, the couple is alienated from each other because Port fears the consequences of commitment. He is "unable to break out of the cage into which he had shut himself from love" (Bowles, 1990, p. 78). His wife might be unable or unwilling to get him to make that marital commitment, even though she seems to be committed to him since her life revolves around his. The narrator says that "she always did everything that required a conscious effort, for Port" (Bowles, 1990, p. 35). Port sees himself as the protagonist of a piece of fiction or drama, while Kit is the spectator watching every move he does (Bowles, 1990, p. 18). This is made evident when Kit tells him that the difference between them is that he can live alone and does

not need the presence of anyone in his life, while she cannot stand that. And probably this is why she succumbs to Tunner's charms when Port is drifting apart from her, and falls in love with Belqasim after Port dies. She does not know what to do or how to be alone.

Moreover, they seem to be disconnected from life around them. The adventurous journey they have undertaken is intended to help them find meaning in their purposeless lives, even though they do not share the same views and aspirations in life. Port defines their plight as follows: "we've never managed, either one of us, to get all the way into life. We're hanging on to the outside for all we're worth, convinced we're going to fall off the next bump" (Bowles, 1990, p. 79). The Moresbys are in a state of existential despair, and their nihilistic tendencies increase as they advance through the empty deep desert which is a parallel to consciousness. According to Jean-Paul Sartre:

When you live alone you no longer know what it is to tell a story: the plausible disappears at the same time as the friends. You let events flow by too: you suddenly see people appear who speak and then go away; you plunge into stories of which you can't make head or tail: you'd make a terrible witness. (Sartre and Alexander, 1964)

The Sheltering Sky is a road novel where travel is synonymous of self-discovery. The couple is detached from time and space. They belong to nowhere, but they keep moving on to find out who they really are. The desert is the right place to find the truth they long for since they are stripped off of their presumed Western identity. The only thing left for them is the innate instinct of survival. They have to fight their way out of the desert, but the latter will end up defeating them as they are left alone, defenseless and clueless in a strange, harsh and limitless space that does not resemble anything they have ever known. In the same vein, Sartre says:

I am responsible for everything ... except for my very responsibility, for I am not the foundation of my being. Therefore everything takes place as if I were compelled to be responsible. I am abandoned in the world ... in the sense that I find myself suddenly alone and without help, engaged in a

world for which I bear the whole responsibility without being able, whatever I do, to tear myself away from this responsibility for an instant. (Sartre, 1956)

Therefore, if they survive the journey, they will be reborn out of the nothingness of the vast desert. Nothingness is, in fact, their biggest fear. It is what drove them to North African Sahara. The following passage illustrates this idea:

"You know," said Port, and his voice sounded unreal, as voices are likely to do after a long pause in an utterly silent spot, "the sky here's very strange. I often have the sensation when I look at it that it's a solid thing up there, protecting us from what's behind."

Kit shuddered slightly as she said: "From what's behind?"

"Yes."

"But what is behind?" Her voice was very small.

"Nothing, I suppose. Just darkness. Absolute night". (Bowles, 1990, p. 79)

The nothingness that is suggested in this context resembles the nothingness evoked by Kurtz' most expressive phrase: "the horror", at the end of Conrad's *Heart of Darkness* (1994), which also chronicles a journey of self-discovery. The nothingness beyond the sky is ambivalent. It refers to the abysmal desert and to the "glacial deadness" Port feels at the centre of his being (Bowles, 1990, p. 115), and the obliteration facing him at the end of his fatal illness.

Conclusion

Paul Bowles's *The Sheltering Sky* serves as a profound exploration of both physical and psychological journeys, where the vast and desolate Sahara desert becomes a powerful symbol of the inner void faced by the protagonists. Through Port and Kit Moresby's harrowing experiences, Bowles delves into themes of alienation, existential despair, and the search for meaning in a world that offers no easy answers. Their journey is not just a geographical one but a descent into the depths of their own psyches, where they confront the nothingness that looms both in the desert around them and within themselves. The novel ultimately reflects Bowles' critique of modern Western civilization, portraying the desert as a space where cultural identities are stripped away, leaving the characters to grapple with their most basic instincts and fears. Ultimately, *The Sheltering Sky* underscores the absurdity of life, as the characters' search for meaning leads them only to the realization of life's inherent emptiness, highlighting the pervasive existential despair that defines much of Bowles's work.

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